

Critical thinking and research skills as dimensions to cognitive competence in a research course

Raymond L. Santiago^{1*}, Melbert V. Animas¹, Nilda W. Balsicas²

¹School of International Hospitality and Tourism Management, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines

²Office of the Vice President for Research, Extension, and Linkages, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines

*Corresponding author: raymond_santiago@sdca.edu.ph

Abstract

This paper explored the influences of critical thinking and research skills in attainment of student learning outcomes in a research course. In this paper, critical thinking and research skills are viewed as dimensions to cognitive competence. Results of the study showed that students perceived that among the research skills, they are good at gathering data. They also perceived that their thinking skill is best demonstrated at respecting the work of others. The researchers believed that those students who have acquired good critical thinking skills are also good in conducting research which becomes highly useful for them. However, there are a number of limitations that need to be considered such that further review is needed to elucidate the concept of cognitive competence in critical thinking and research skills dimensions. Although literature review showed that both critical thinking and research tasks are interrelated, more empirical research on their relationships is needed. Furthermore, while there was an initial validation to the instrument, it is necessary to further validate its content and reliability. Lastly, the same study may be conducted in other research classes and in various majors to have more vigorous studies to evaluate and compare results.

Keywords: *Critical thinking; research; cognitive competence; exploratory study.*

To cite this article:

Santiago, R. L., Animas, M. V., & Balsicas, N. W. (2021). Critical thinking and research skills as dimensions to cognitive competence in a research course. *Hospitalite*, 5, 1-7.

Introduction

Acquisition of research skills remains difficult for students who have been exposed to research activities in the previous years. Once formal research course is already a required course not only as part of an activity of a subject, students find research activities as something they knew but needed more practice. In research course class, students were exposed to various research tasks such as lectures and activities aligned with learning outcomes. These include the lecture of the basics such as developing a title of study, writing the introductory part, finding a research gap, synthesizing the ideas based on the related literature, up to writing references using the College format. After the lecture, this is usually accompanied with several practice activities to check on the attainment of learning outcomes including critiquing of student outputs. The final activity is developing and presenting their research study to the panel. With these activities, the researchers would like to investigate whether research skills and critical thinking skills collectively term as cognitive competence are able to influence the attainment of student learning outcomes in research course.

Why critical thinking? According to Sun and Hui (2012) there were studies that critical thinking is beneficial to cognitive development, lifelong learning, and accomplishment. In this study critical thinking is premised to facilitate abilities of the students in performing the research tasks in association with research skills.

Critical thinking and research skills as cognitive competence

The study explored critical thinking and research skills as dimensions to cognitive competence. According to Piaget (1962, 1977), individuals with cognitive competence can influence their own experiences as well as organize and adjust their thoughts to lead their behavior through a cyclical process of assimilation and accommodation (Esa, 2015). Similarly, Fry (1992, as cited by Sun and Hui, 2012) said that cognitive competence is made up of three interconnected and interdependent components: cognitive structures, cognitive processes, and overt behaviors. Cognitive processes including metacognition, self-regulation styles, and cognitive skills like thinking, reasoning, problem-solving, and information processing are among them. It further says that people can influence their cognitive development and potential by manipulating their mental processes and cognitive styles through the application of proper thinking skills. It is also believed that cognitive competence entails the ability to absorb, self-regulate, and transfer cognitive skills in order to construct knowledge and make sense of the environment, rather than just manipulating and strategizing information (Vygotsky, as cited by Sun and Hui, 2012). According to Kassymova et al. (2019), the effect of the e-learning education system on students' cognition was recognized, and it was said that cognitive competence is necessary to build among students. Said descriptions are the essence of research tasks in a formal class. By embedding the critical thinking skills in research tasks, these may comprise the core competence, since critical thinking can be effectively taught or developed through research education.

On critical thinking skills

What is critical thinking? According to Paul (1993), it is a type of thinking that is engaged in solving problems, generating inferences, calculating likelihoods, and making decisions, and it relates to the use of cognitive skills or strategies that increase the chance of desired outcomes. It influences the mastery of learning goals and deep information processing (Phan, 2009). As a result, a critical thing is a process that activates particular cognitive skills in order to make the best decisions about what to believe and do (Flage, 2003).

On research skills

Brew and Boud (1995) claimed that the process of inquiry is universal to both learning and research. Students are motivated by inquiry-based teaching because it allows them to learn "about and through research" (Jenkins et al., 2003 as cited by Yeoman & Zamorski, 2008). Yeoman and Zamorski (2008) said that research is active, exciting and dynamic and that innovation, independence, problem-solving, critical thinking, and the ability to handle knowledge in a variety of ways are all research capabilities. These research capabilities require a wider body of knowledge and techniques within the discipline, and higher cognitive skills (Roach et al., 2000).

Given the common characteristics of critical thinking and research skills which included use of cognitive or strategies such as solving problem, inferring, and hypothesizing, this combination can be viewed as dimensions of cognitive competence. Furthermore, it is viewed in this study that critical thinking is a facilitator in the performance of research skills (Ventista, 2019). Critical thinking and research skills as dimensions to cognitive competence become comparable to de Bono's concepts of "lateral thinking" and "vertical thinking" (de Bono, 1991 as cited by Sun & Hui, 2012 and Shek & Yu, 2016) in which the former requires people to examine things from different viewpoints and come up with new ideas, whilst the latter requires people to look at things sequentially and conventionally and find solutions after a thorough analysis. Hence, each thinking complements one another in providing solutions to a problem.

In this study, it is premised that critical thinking and research skills are dimensions to cognitive competence that facilitate the attainment of student learning outcomes during COVID-19 pandemic in a

research course. The study attempted to investigate the influences of critical thinking and research skills as cognitive competence. Cognitive competence in this study refers to the combination of critical thinking and research skills in research classes delivered entirely online. Specifically, this study would like to determine the level of perceptions to their abilities as regards to a) critical thinking and b) the research skills in performing the research tasks and to determine if there is a significant relationship between critical thinking and research skills. The output of this study could be used to improve the research course modules by enhancing its contents by explicitly embedding critical thinking activities and research skills development activities to attain target student learning outcomes.

Methods

The study attempted to investigate the influences of critical thinking and Research Tasks as cognitive competence. In this study, embedded approach was used (Sun and Hui, 2012). Embedded approach means that critical thinking and research skills are integrated in a research course. This method allows students to use critical and research tasks in a meaningful context in a subject while also developing a thorough comprehension of the subject matter by putting the skills to utilize in reasoning, making inferences, and generating creative and valuable ideas.

Sixty-five (65) third year students were the respondents enrolled in research course during the first semester of the Academic Year 2020-2021 in which lessons were delivered entirely online. Students registered in the course had completed five professional courses related to hospitality and tourism management in the previous semesters.

Delivery of lessons was entirely online, however, ensuring that student learning outcomes were met. For example, the teachers discussed the research topics with the aid of learning modules and via various platforms. Learning activities are delivered remotely by the students in different applications such as Zoom, Google Meet, Blackboard, and through e-mails. In this study, research and practice activities included those of organizing notes, attending tutorial classes, completing formative exercises in research, reading assigned articles, re-reading the articles for better understanding, listening and taking notes of the lecture, writing introductory draft, defining variables, and formulating hypotheses. Critical thinking activities also include identifying the problem in an article, gathering of data, analyzing and interpreting data, and critiquing the work of other researchers, in addition to identifying research gaps and formulating conclusions and implications.

The instrument was composed of eight statements on critical thinking skills acquired and nine statements on research practices and activities. The instrument was expert validated by two faculty members, one from the Education and the other from Psychology. It was pilot tested to students in higher year who have already completed the research course. The instrument was modified according to the suggestion and results of the pilot testing. A link via Google Forms was administered to sixty-five (65) students who were enrolled in research course which was entirely delivered in online due to pandemic.

Results and Discussion

The study explored the influence of critical thinking and research skills as cognitive competence in attainment of student learning outcomes during the Research course.

Perceived skills in critical thinking

Table 1 shows the level of perceptions of the students towards their critical thinking skills. The students “moderately agree” that they can ask good questions (Mean: 5.18, SD: 1.25); “moderately agree” that they can identify related and relevant literature or studies (Mean: 5.17, SD: 1.34); “moderately agree” that they can integrate the ideas and concepts of various authors into one big idea (Mean: 5.12, SD: 1.38); “moderately agree” that they know how to put ideas of different authors into one (Mean: 5.05, SD: 1.32); “moderately agree” that they learned how to read and reread research articles (Mean: 5.20, SD: 1.23); “agree” to learn how to be more patient in their tasks (Mean: 5.51, SD: 1.29); “agree” that they have improved their writing abilities (Mean: 5.32, SD: 1.35); “agree” to learn how to respect the work of others or intellectual property rights (Mean: 5.65, SD: 1.40); “agree” that they have learned using social network and information tools in gathering and sharing information (Mean: 5.62, SD: 1.31); “agree” that they can now distinguish a good information from a bad one (Mean: 5.40, SD: 1.23); “agree” that they learn how to pay close attention to details (Mean: 5.43, SD: 1.29); “agree” that gathering the most important information being presented to the study will help them to summarize and cite it in writing (Mean: 5.47; SD: 1.35).

Among the critical thinking skills, the study has shown that majority of the students perceived that they learn how to respect the work of others or intellectual property rights. It means that they agree that they know how to respect the work of others. Said result is supported by what Paul (1993) mentioned about critical thinking as “the use of cognitive skills or strategies that increase the probability of a desirable outcome,” and by Flage (2003) that critical thinking is a process that sparks certain cognitive strategies to enable us to arrive at best decisions.

Table 1. Mean and standard deviation to the perceived abilities in critical thinking skills

Critical thinking skills	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. I can ask good questions.	5.18	1.25	MA
2. I can identify related and relevant literature or studies.	5.17	1.34	MA
3. I can integrate the ideas and concepts of various authors into one big idea.	5.12	1.38	MA
4. I know how to put ideas of different authors into one.	5.05	1.32	MA
5. I learned how to read and reread research articles.	5.20	1.35	MA
6. I learned how to be more patient in my tasks.	5.51	1.29	A
7. I have improved my writing ability.	5.32	1.35	A
8. I learn how to respect the work of others or intellectual property rights.	5.65	1.40	A
9. I have learned using social network and information tools in gathering and sharing information.	5.62	1.31	A
10. I can now distinguish a good information from a bad one.	5.40	1.23	A
11. I learn how to pay close attention to details.	5.43	1.29	A
12. I learn that gathering the most important information being presented to the study will help me to summarize and cite it in writing.	5.46	1.35	A
Average Mean	5.22	1.26	MA

Legend: 1.00-1.85 – Strongly Disagree (SD); 1.86-2.71 – Disagree (D); 2.72-3.57 – Moderately Disagree (MD); 3.58-4.43 – Not sure (NS); 4.44-5.29 – Moderately Agree (MA); 5.30-6.15 – Agree (A); 6.16-7.00 – Strongly Agree (SA)

Perceived skills in research

Table 2 shows the perception of the students towards research skills. The students “moderately agree” that they can easily identify the problem (Mean: 5.28, SD: 1.38); “agree” that they know how to gather data (Mean: 5.35, SD: 1.30); “moderately agree” that they know how to analyze and interpret data (Mean: 5.12, SD: 1.41); “moderately agree” that they know how to identify relevant assumptions from a problem (Mean: 5.25, SD: 1.35); “moderately agree” that they know how to challenge assumptions of another research (Mean: 5.12, SD: 1.35); “moderately agree” that they are now aware of the possible biases

in research (Mean: 5.17, SD: 1.43); “moderately agree” they are now aware of the possible biases in research (Mean: 5.17, SD: 1.43); “moderately agree” that they can make decisions using the results of the research (Mean: 5.15, SD: 1.34); and “moderately agree” that they can understand the information received and present information in a manner other can understand (Mean: 5.29, SD: 1.39).

The results further show that the students “agree” that they have acquired their critical thinking skills. This skill perceived by students support the descriptions of the acquisition of research skills as proposed by Fitts and Posner (1967) which was cited by You and Bednarski (2014) that students may have reached the cognitive stage and learned what to do, how to do it, and when to do it in order to attain the skill's objectives. Listening to instructions and receiving feedback on errors, as well as didactic courses, seminars, reading books and papers, and informal guidance from peers, mentors, and other researchers, all contributed to a high level of cognitive activity.

Table 2. Mean and standard deviation to the perceived abilities in research skills

Research skills	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. I can easily identify the problem.	5.28	1.38	MA
2. I know how to gather data.	5.35	1.30	A
3. I know how to analyze and interpret data.	5.12	1.41	MA
4. I know how to identify relevant assumptions from a problem.	5.25	1.35	MA
5. I challenge assumptions of another research.	5.12	1.35	MA
6. I am now aware of the possible biases in research.	5.17	1.43	MA
7. I can make decisions using the results of the research.	5.15	1.34	MA
8. I can understand the information receive and present information in a manner other can understand.	5.29	1.39	MA
Average Mean	5.30	1.25	A

Legend: 1.00-1.85 – Strongly Disagree (SD); 1.86-2.71 – Disagree (D); 2.72-3.57 – Moderately Disagree (MD); 3.58-4.43 – Not sure (NS); 4.44-5.29 – Moderately Agree (MA); 5.30-6.15 – Agree (A); 6.16-7.00 – Strongly Agree (SA)

Relationship between critical thinking and research skills

Table 3 shows the correlation results between students’ perceived critical thinking and research skills acquired. Using Pearson–correlation r, results showed that there is a significant relationship between critical thinking activities and research skills acquired ($r = .880, p = .000$). This indicates that critical thinking skills are associated with the research skills.

The results showed that the research and critical thinking skills of students are significantly correlated. It means that both skills are closely associated in developing the cognitive competence of the students and in attaining the student learning outcomes in research. Critical thinking may have influenced the development of the research abilities consequently performing the research tasks. It further showed that students who have acquired good critical thinking skills are also good in research. Said result can be similar to what Fry pointed that cognitive structures, cognitive processes, and overt behaviors are all intertwined and interrelated components of cognitive competence. Among them are cognitive processes like metacognition, cognitive styles of self-regulation, and cognitive skills of thinking, reasoning, analyzing problems, and information processing. It goes on to explain that people can influence their cognitive development and potential by controlling their mental processes and cognitive styles through the application of proper thinking skills such as in research skills and in critical thinking skills.

Table 3. Correlation results between critical thinking and research skills

		Critical Thinking Skills	Research Skills
Critical Thinking Skills	Pearson Correlation	1	.880**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	65	65
Research Skills	Pearson Correlation	.880**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	65	65

**Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Conclusion and Recommendation

In this paper, critical thinking and research skills are described as dimensions in cognitive competence. Embedding these skills in a research can facilitate attainment of learning outcomes in a research course. Students perceived that among the research skills, they are good at gathering data. They also perceived that their critical thinking skills are best demonstrated at respecting the work of others. The researchers believed that those students who have acquired good critical thinking skills are also good in conducting research or their research skill is highly useful. However, there are a number of limitations that need to be considered: First, as the narrow definition of critical thinking and research skills were adopted, more research is required to further understand the concept of cognitive competence. Second, while a study of the literature revealed that critical thinking and research activities are related, additional empirical research on the subject is needed. Furthermore, while there was an initial validation to the instrument, it is necessary to further validate its content and reliability. Moreover, the same study may be conducted in other research classes and in various majors to have more vigorous studies to determine and compare results. Lastly, the study was conducted during COVID-19 pandemic. It is recommended to conduct a study about impact of the pandemic to research performance of the students. It is hoped that the results can improve the content of the research curriculum particularly in the context of e-learning.

References

- Brew, A., & Boud, D. (1995). Teaching and research: Establishing the vital link with learning. *Higher Education*, 29, 261-273. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01384493>
- De Bono, E. (1991). The direct teaching of thinking in education and the CoRT method. In S. Maclure (Ed.), *Learning to think: Thinking to learn* (pp. 3-14). Pergamom Press.
- Esa, M. B. (2015). *The influence of project manager's cognitive styles on project success in the Malaysian construction industry* (Master's thesis, University of Malaya). http://studentsrepo.um.edu.my/5524/1/MuneeraEsa_BHA090005.pdf
- Flage, D. E. (2003). *The art of questioning: An introduction to critical thinking*. Pearson.
- Fry, P. S. (1992). *Fostering children's cognitive competence through mediated learning experiences: Frontiers and futures*. Charles C. Thomas Publishing Ltd.
- Jenkins, A., Breen, R., Brew, A., & Lindsay, R. (2003). *Reshaping teaching in higher education: Linking teaching with research*. Kogan Page.
- Kassymova, G. K., Duisenbayeva, Sh. S., Adilbayeva, U. B., Khalenova A. R., Kosherbayeva, A. N., Triyono, M. B., & Sangilbayev, O. S. (2019). Cognitive competence based on the e-learning. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, 28(18), 167-177. <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=45528841>
- Paul, R. W. (1993). The logic of creative and critical thinking. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 37(1), 27-39. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002764293037001004>

- Phan, H. P. (2009). Exploring students' reflective thinking practice, deep processing strategies, effort, and achievement goal orientations. *Educational Psychology*, 29(3), 297–313. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01443410902877988>
- Piaget, J. (1962). *The language and thought of the child* (3rd ed.). Routledge & Kegan-Paul.
- Piaget, J. (1977). *The development of thought: Equilibration of cognitive structures*. Blackwell.
- Roach, M., Blackmore, P. and Dempster, J. (2000). *Supporting high level learning through research-based methods: Interim guidelines for course design*. TELRI Project Centre for Academic Practice.
- Shek, D. T., & Yu, L. (2016). Cognitive competence: A key positive youth development construct for university students. *International Journal on Disability and Human Development*, 15(2), 135-142. <https://doi.org/10.1515/ijdh-2016-0702>
- Sun, R. C. F. & Hui, E. K. P. (2012). Cognitive competence as a positive youth development construct: A conceptual review. *The Scientific World Journal*, 2012, 210953. <https://doi.org/10.1100/2012/210953>
- Ventista, O. (2019). *An evaluation of the 'Philosophy for Children' programme: The impact on cognitive and non-cognitive skills* (Doctoral dissertation, Durham University). http://etheses.dur.ac.uk/13121/1/Ventista_Thesis.pdf?DDD29+
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1962). *Thought and language*. MIT Press.
- Vygotsky, L. S., Cole, M., John-Steiner, V., Scribner, S., & Souberman, E. (1978). *Mind in society: The development of higher psychological process*. Harvard University Press.
- Yeoman, K. H., & Zamorski, B. (2008). Investigating the impact on skill development of an undergraduate scientific research skills course. *Bioscience Education*, 11(1), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.3108/beej.11.5>
- You, Y. N., & Bednarski, B. (2014). Developing a research skill set. *Clinics in Colon and Rectal Surgery*, 27(2), 48-54. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0034-1376168>